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New Iron(III) Complexes with Dibasic Tridentate ONO Donor Schiff Bases Derived from Salicylaldehyde, Substituted Salicylaldehyde and Alcoholamines

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In recent years the magnetic exchange interactions in transition metal complexes have been the subject of many investigations¹⁻⁵. These studies have mostly veered around $S = \frac{1}{2}$ systems and far fewer studies have been reported on $S = 1, 2, 3/2$ and $5/2$ systems. The iron(III) complexes ($S = 5/2$ system) of Schiff bases serve as models for biologically important compounds like haemerythrin and haem protein systems. Although in copper(II) and oxovanadium(IV) complexes of I, the magnetic properties of the complexes are quite different in $n = 2$ and 3 complexes⁶⁻⁷, such difference has not been observed in the iron(III) complexes^{8,9}. The substitution of hydrogen atoms in methylene linkage in I may influence the magnetic properties of iron(III) complexes of I and no such study has so far been reported. In order to know the effect of substitution in the methylene linkage and also on the effect of size of the chelate ring on the magnetic properties of iron(III) complexes we have synthesized several new iron(III) complexes of tridentate dibasic Schiff bases(II) and (III). A comparison of magnetic properties of iron(III) complexes of the ligands (I-III) is presented.

I. $n = 2, 3$

Experimental

Salicylaldehyde and ethanolamine were of BDH reagent grade. 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and isopropanolamine were the products of Fluka AG, Switzerland. 2-Amino-2-methylpropanol was purchased from Koch-Light Lab., England. Propanolamine was obtained from Aldrich Chemical Co., U. S. A. Anhydrous ferric chloride was obtained from BDH.

Iron was determined by potassium dichromate¹⁰ after decomposing the complex with concentrated nitric acid and then igniting to Fe_2O_3 . Chlorine was determined gravimetrically as AgCl after fusing the complex in a nickel crucible with sodium peroxide and sodium hydroxide mixture. The elemental analyses were done by the microanalytical services of the University of Bombay. Infrared spectra were recorded in nujol mulls on Beckman IR 20 and Perkin-Elmer 620 infrared spectrophotometers. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out by a Gouy balance using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as the calibrant. The diamagnetic corrections were calculated by using Pascal's constants. The conductance measurements were carried out in tetrahydrofuran solution (0.001M) using Toshniwal type CLO-C₂A conductivity bridge and a dip type cell. The molecular weight measurements were carried out by the Rast method¹¹ using diphenyl as the solvent. We have noticed that diphenyl is a better solvent in comparison to camphor in terms of reproducibility, and the molal boiling point elevation constant of diphenyl was found to be 6.8.

General method of preparation of the complexes :

Salicylaldehyde or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (0.02 mol) was condensed with the equimolar amount of the appropriate alkanolamine by refluxing in 30-60 ml absolute alcohol for 30 mins to give the yellow Schiff base solution. Anhydrous ferric chloride (3.24 g, 0.02 mol) was dissolved in 30 ml of absolute alcohol. To this the Schiff base solution was added and the mixture was refluxed for 2 hr. The separated reddish brown precipitates were suction filtered, washed with absolute alcohol and dried *in vacuo* at room temperature. Yield = 15%.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data for complexes (Table I) indicate that the metal : ligand ratio is 1 : 1. The electrolytic conductance measurements in tetrahydrofuran show that the complexes are non-electrolytes ($\Lambda_M = 8 - 13 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mole}^{-1}$). The ir spectra of the complexes do not exhibit any $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ band. This shows that there is no water molecule present in the complexes and both the replaceable hydrogen atoms of the ligands are

NOTES

TABLE 1—THE ANALYTICAL, INFRARED SPECTRA, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND MOLECULAR WEIGHT DATA OF IRON(III) COMPLEXES OF SCHIFF BASES^{a,b}

Complex	Found (Calcd.)%					$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ cm^{-1}	$\nu(\text{Fe}-\text{Cl})$ cm^{-1}	Temp. k	$\chi_{\text{M}}^{\text{Corr}}$ (10^{-6}) cgs	μ_{eff} B.M.	Molecular weight Found, Calcd.)
	C	H	N	Cl	Fe						
[Fe(Cl)(sal-isopropanolamine)] ₂	43.8 (44.73)	4.2 (4.10)	5.2 (5.22)	13.5 (13.23)	20.3 (:0.22)	1625	360	301	10677	5.09	493(537)
[Fe(Cl)(sal-2-amino-2-methyl-propanol)] ₂	45.6 (46.77)	5.0 (4.60)	4.8 (4.96)	13.0 (12.57)	19.8 (19.78)	1615	370	300	10589	5.06	542(565)
[Fe(Cl)(hydrox-ethanolamine)] ₂	50.3 (51.26)	3.9 (3.61)	4.7 (4.61)	11.4 (11.67)	18.1 (18.35)	1600	360	299	11847	5.35	583(609)
[Fe(Cl)(hydrox-propanolamine)] ₂	52.5 (52.77)	4.4 (4.08)	4.5 (4.40)	11.2 (11.15)	17.2 (17.54)	1610	350	299	7839	4.35	606(637)
[Fe(Cl)(hydrox-isopropanolamine)] ₂	51.4 (52.77)	4.1 (4.08)	4.4 (4.40)	11.2 (11.15)	17.7 (17.54)	1605	352	299	11619	5.29	577(637)
[Fe(Cl)(hydrox-2-amino-2-methylpropanol)] ₂	53.6 (54.18)	4.8 (4.51)	4.1 (4.51)	11.0 (10.69)	16.5 (16.81)	1605	355	299	10581	5.05	621(665)

(a) Abbreviations : sal=salicylaldehyde, hydrox=2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde.

(b) The effective magnetic moment was calculated using the Curie equation : $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.84 (\chi_{\text{M}}^{\text{corr}} \times T)^{1/2}$ B.M.

deprotonated. This reflects the dibasic nature of these ligands. The $\nu(\text{Fe}-\text{Cl})$ stretch is observed at 360 cm^{-1} in these complexes^{1,2} (Table 1). The non-electrolytic nature of the complexes and the occurrence of a Fe-Cl band in the far ir spectra indicate that the chlorine is coordinated to iron(III) and is not ionic in nature. The molecular weight data demonstrate that these complexes are dimeric in nature and hence the complexes can be formulated as $[\text{FeCl}]_2$.

The bands around 1610 cm^{-1} in the complexes can be attributed to the coordinated $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ involving coordination through the nitrogen atom of the azomethine group since the free C=N stretch is known to appear at around 1640 cm^{-1} in aromatic Schiff bases^{13,14}. In the complexes the $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{Fe}-\text{O}-\text{Fe})$ band cannot be assigned unambiguously due to the interference of the ligand bands in the region $810-870 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ^{16,15}.

All the complexes exhibit the effective magnetic moments in the range 4.35-5.35 B.M. at room temperature (Table 1). The TIP contribution was taken as zero for a $^6A_{1g}$ ground term¹⁶. The magnetic moment values are lower than the spin-only moment of 5.9 B.M. expected for high-spin iron(III) complexes. The complexes show similar magnetic behaviour as the iron(III) complexes of (I) and are involved in antiferromagnetic exchange via d^5-d^5 superexchange pathways in Fe-O-Fe bridge^{8,9}. The substitution of the hydrogen atoms of the methylene linkage does not influence the magnetic properties of iron(III) complexes of I, II and III. The substitution at the benzene ring of the salicylaldehyde moiety also does not effect the magnetic properties of the complexes and this indicates that the electronic effect of substitution in iron(III) complexes is relatively unimportant except for any structural modifications they produce in

the $\text{M} \begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \diagdown \\ \diagdown \text{O} \diagup \end{array} \text{M}$ via alteration of molecular pack-

ing¹⁷. The present study also confirms that the chelate ring size close to the bridging oxygen atoms does not influence the magnetic properties of iron(III) complexes of I, II and III. The single crystal X-ray structure determination of the iron(III) complex of I ($n=3$) indicates that the oxygen atoms of the propanolamine are the bridging atoms and the complex is a dimer⁸. On the basis of ir, magnetic and molecular weight data we suggest a five coordinated square pyramidal structure with

dimeric oxobridging $(\text{Fe} \begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \diagdown \\ \diagdown \text{O} \diagup \end{array} \text{Fe})$ for the iron(III)

complexes of II and III^{8,9}. The comparable magnetic properties of iron(III) complexes of I, II and III indicates that the structures, Fe-Fe distance and Fe-O-Fe angle are similar in these complexes.

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